

CHARACTERISTICS OF MODULAR TEACHING TECHNOLOGY IN MUSIC EDUCATION

Zikriyayev Mardon Makhamatjon ugli

Art Institute named after Botir Zakirov under the State Conservatory of
Uzbekistan Department of interfaculty piano performance
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10183922>

Abstract: The effectiveness of modular teaching technologies in improving the professional competence of future music teachers constitutes the content of this article. The relevance of the modular approach to the training of the future music teacher is to use the opportunity to analyze the labor market, to identify the acute professional needs of practice that were not previously provided by practical training.

Key words: modular teaching technology, competence, music teacher, higher education.

In modern society, higher education has become one of the important areas of human activity. The reason for such attention is the understanding that the most important value and main capital of modern society is the training of a specialist capable of searching for and mastering new knowledge and making non-standard decisions. An important direction of modern pedagogical science is the search for tools and conditions that ensure the improvement of the effectiveness of the teacher training process. In this regard, our President Sh. Mirziyoev's opinion that "*We consider it our first duty to improve the activities of all links of the education and training system based on the requirements of today's time*" places a great responsibility on the pedagogues of higher education operating in the education system. The development of social life presents the educational system of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the issue of implementing a number of very important and urgent tasks. Some of these include: radically improving the quality of education, solving the problems of connection and coherence between subjects, inter-subjects, educational stages, ensuring that education is open to all, and accelerating the processes of integration with the developed scientific and educational environment of the world. Can be shown. In order to solve such problems, the introduction of modular teaching technologies into the educational process serves to reveal the following opportunities in education:

The education system of our country faces a number of important tasks, such as improving the quality and efficiency of education, its openness, humanism and individual orientation, ensuring the coherence of all levels of education, and its integration with the world educational environment. put the issue of performing urgent tasks transversely.

The fulfillment of the tasks set before the general education schools, which provide education and upbringing to the personality of the student, depends, first of all, on the quality training of pedagogues in higher education institutions. The level of competence of specialists, professional skills, the ability to correctly and purposefully manage pedagogical processes determine the success of forming the student's personality. This system of higher pedagogic education, in general, all organizations responsible for education and personnel training, sets the urgent task of further researching the issues of professional training of future pedagogues to organize and manage the processes of educating a well-rounded person.

In order to achieve these goals, it is necessary to further strengthen the educational and methodological base of the higher education system, to further improve the conditions for students to acquire comprehensive intellectual knowledge, and to increase the scientific potential and professional competence of personnel.

Art is one of the most important and priority criteria determining the level of socio-economic, spiritual and educational development of a particular country, society, as an integral part of any national culture according to its nature and social content.

Education in the field of art, what should it be?

In recent years, the attention and respect paid to artists by the head of our state has encouraged the work of representatives of the industry, increased the social responsibility of each artist, and encouraged them to look at their work from a new perspective. In particular, in the decision "On approval of the concept of further deepening of national culture" adopted by the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the principles of continuity and succession between education and special creative-professional programs in the system of training qualified personnel in the field of culture and art it was specifically noted that the individual teaching method is not used effectively in teaching students.

Musical ability.

It is known that at the initial stage of learning music, much attention is paid to its development in the musical educational process, and specific musical abilities are the leading determinant. In the work "*Psychology of Musical Abilities*" B.M. Teplov writes: "*Musical ability*" as a part of musical activity is a set of individual psychological characteristics, unlike any other music, but at the same time associated with any type of musical activity expressed his opinion.

The first common problem faced by the modern music education teacher is related to the variability and limitations of the proposed program. Pedagogical problem situations often arise from the fact that the teacher does not understand how to use all the educational tools he should have, for example, working plans. This is especially true for music teachers in regional educational institutions and in higher education who do not have sufficient professional skills. They are in such a situation that technical means (*video projector, electronic board, etc.*) are often not given to the teacher even if they are in the school. , even when given, it follows that the teacher does not have the ability to use it. If we are talking about district areas, it seems that it is very difficult to independently search for such tools, in most cases there is no attempt at all. Authors do not publish materials necessary for teachers in open electronic copy, new collections are not always available in bookstores, but only old copies can be found in libraries, however, not always finding new musical works This problem is becoming more urgent due to the competence requirements offered to music teachers.

The second general problem that characterizes the activity of a music education teacher in modern conditions is the variability of teaching methods recommended in the main educational and methodological sets and other materials, and sometimes in abstract conditions, in the methods of their implementation, they are not always professional preparation, the use of music selections in certain working conditions. At the same time, the inability to demonstrate in practice the existing large-scale activities of music teaching, education and personal development with the help of music in open lessons and in the process of implementing other forms of lessons.

The third generalized problem is the lack of qualifications of teachers in the field of teaching, educating and developing children's musical abilities at a high level during music lessons. The lack of general instructions for the types of activities that should be included in the content of music lessons in modern educational and methodological complexes. At the same time, the lack of specific recommendations and algorithms for the selection and application of existing methods, the formation of optimal complexes of methods and tools, and the lack of skills to approach these aspects creatively. The methodology of teaching students musical literacy, solfeggio, one- and two-voice and other types of musical activities has not been thoroughly developed by local musicians and teachers.

Such problematic components of professional activity can be studied by the method of educational situations in the conditions of modular teaching at the university.

The criteria for the formation of the module are as follows: the ability to teach the module as a part of various subjects and as an independent lesson while maintaining the right of content and practical value; the possibility of restructuring it in accordance with its goals and objectives, the needs and requirements of employers. Providing such flexibility of the educational module makes it suitable for different professional groups - students of elementary music education, and also a graduate who may be interested in scientific research, methodological interest in this module, i.e. future music teacher. Allows use in teacher training. The types of educational modules can be used as a tool for the formation of pedagogical competencies related to the labor market within the framework of professional development for practicing teachers, administrative staff of educational institutions and methodologists of general and vocational education institutions.

The purpose of the modular programs is definitely to train a qualified specialist. Creating a module program begins with determining the system of requirements for this specialist. Today, after studying the system of general requirements for a future music teacher, we can divide them into three main groups. The criteria for determining the competence of a music teacher can be divided into the following categories.

According to pedagogues, if teaching is properly organized on the basis of module technology, students at any stage of education will learn new educational materials, improve their skills and qualifications. The module is developed on the basis of an algorithm and includes the following components: a specific goal, theoretical knowledge, practical training, methodological guidance, supervision, mastered knowledge, testing and evaluation of skills and etc.

Training based on module technology is carried out in the following sequence:

- 1. analysis of initial conditions in modular training;*
- 2. defining the educational goals and content of the module;*
- 3. preparation of educational and didactic materials and teaching tools;*
- 4. conducting theoretical and practical training;*
- 5. assessment of students' acquired theoretical knowledge and practical skills.*

All of the above is aimed at expanding the level of thinking of students, understanding the cause of events, and teaching them to search. The essence of the module system lies in the fact that students learn the modules of individual units of education in a consistent sequence.

Analysis of initial conditions in modular training. The use of a modular system in musicology provides an opportunity to quickly develop and implement a new modular unit instead of an old one. The advantage of education in music science based on the module

system is that more attention is paid to the learner, his independent work on himself, and self-control. The duration of training based on the module system depends on the training of the learner and the level of his desire to acquire professional qualifications. Training can be stopped after the desired model of training.

In order to prepare for the teaching of music science based on module technology, that is, to organize theoretical and practical training, work will be carried out in three directions.

First of all, the state of preparation of students is analyzed, their knowledge, the level and ability of mastering educational materials is determined. Because their self-confidence, ability, personal status, and age have a certain influence on their education. Based on the classification of students according to their abilities, they are recommended to learn the subject independently. Secondly, the existing conditions are analyzed. It includes the following: legal conditions; In this, the curriculum and programs related to the educational process are studied. Conditions related to the organization of the educational process; In this, the place and other conditions of the theoretical and practical training included in the module are studied. Technical conditions; In this, the availability and condition of technical equipment and devices, educational and auxiliary audio-visual tools are studied

Thirdly, the topics to be covered are analyzed and various sources, i.e. educational materials, etc., necessary for determining the content of the modules are studied. For example:

- 1) *textbooks, manuals and other literature in the field of music;*
- 2) *scientific literature (electronic textbooks, Internet information) is studied.*

Determining the educational purpose and content of the module in music. In teaching on the basis of module technology, the purpose and content of music education, the purpose and content of modules are determined first. At the end of the educational goals, the knowledge, skills and personal skills that the student should achieve as a result of education are defined. Learning objectives are developed based on the requirements of the network educational standard. The clearer the learning objective of the module, the easier it is to assess the level of achievement.

Preparation of educational and didactic materials and educational tools for the module. Educational didactic materials and educational tools mean information sources and instruments that serve to form knowledge and skills. In the teaching of music science based on modular technology, textual visual tools, such as educational literature, electronic textbooks and lecture texts, handouts, methodical instructions are used as educational didactic materials in theoretical and practical lessons.

Conducting theoretical and practical training. It is recommended to conduct the theoretical exercises included in the module in sequence. In the teaching of music subjects based on module technology, it is necessary to organize lessons in an interesting way. This has a positive effect on the mood of the learners and helps them to be interested in this field or the topic to be studied in the next lessons.

Assessment of students' theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications. In teaching music science based on module technology, students' knowledge and skills should be regularly evaluated in accordance with educational goals. Assessment is based on pedagogical principles and State Education Standards. Through evaluation, the entire learning process of the module and all its competencies are checked for acceptability. This will determine whether modular training is giving the expected result or not. Students are given tasks that

make it possible to think and process information. After each task or exercise, the work is evaluated. An open and honest discussion of the results in groups is also highly effective. At the end of the module study, you should allow time for a final interview. This gives a good opportunity to reflect on the results of students' work, what they did and did not improve.

References:

1. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to further develop the higher education system, April 21, 2017.
2. Ishmukhamedov R. Ways to improve educational efficiency based on innovative technologies.-T.: TSPU. 2005y.
3. Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.
4. Karimova D.A. Fundamentals of musical pedagogical skills.-T.: Economy and finance. 2008
5. Martine Fraytag. – Chorleiting - effizient unt lebensyab||. Gustav Boss Verlag, Kassel, Germaniya 2011.